

INNOVATION AND HEALTHCARE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Innovation can be defined as invention + adoption + diffusion. In healthcare, it may be a novel idea, product, service or care pathway that has clear benefits when compared to what is currently done. Successful innovations often possess two key qualities: they are both usable and desirable. How can proven innovations be quickly and effectively adopted as best practice and taken up across the whole healthcare system? How can the commercial success of our ideas be realised at home rather than abroad, as has too often been the case? This review explores important issues of funding, information governance, interoperability, medical device regulation, procurement, clinical prototyping and the systemic challenge of encouraging and scaling innovation. A legal and methodological definition is given, the essence and modern classifications of innovation are highlighted. An analysis of trends and factors of economic growth of the state in modern conditions was carried out, taking into account the use of innovative technologies. It has been established that innovations make it possible to provide better medical care, achieve a therapeutic result faster and, therefore, restore or improve the patient's original physical status (medical component). They lead to a higher degree of satisfaction with the medical care of the population (social component) and are aimed at paying off the diagnostic and treatment process (economic component). Innovations in healthcare are the end result of the introduction of innovations (discoveries, results of research and development work) in order to obtain economic and social effects. Innovations in the healthcare sector are intended to create effective medicines, modern medical equipment and equipment, new medical diagnostic, therapeutic, rehabilitation technologies, or organizational processes. Innovative development of healthcare requires: the interaction of medical science and practical healthcare, the implementation and implementation of scientific innovations that are in demand in medical activities, the training of professionals capable of implementing scientific developments. Innovation is the process of developing new approaches, technologies and ways of working. This concept is equally applicable both to the means and technologies of work and to the way organizations or individuals behave, work, act. Any innovation starts with a good idea, but it means much more. Innovation is the process of turning a good idea into something that can be used, implemented or achieved and, if possible, bear fruit in the form of better health care and disease prevention. The innovation process is the process of transforming scientific knowledge into innovation, which can be represented as a sequential chain of events, as a result of which innovation is transformed from an idea into a specific product, technology or service and spreads through practical use. In

the innovation process, economic relations are realized between the creators of innovations, owners of resources and consumers of innovations. These relationships are mediated by the movement of venture capital and information.

Key words: innovation, innovative development, innovative technologies, classification of innovations, the importance of innovations in healthcare, professional specialists, economic growth of the state.

Introduction: Scientific and technological progress does not stand still. Now we can no longer imagine our lives without computers, smartphones and other technical gadgets that make our lives much easier. Improving people's health is possible through the use of new technologies in the examination and treatment of patients. Today, making a diagnosis and treating various diseases is much faster than 20-30 years ago. Innovation in healthcare is a broad term. In its simplest form, it can be defined as the creation and implementation of concepts, ideas, technologies, processes and services that benefit clinical outcomes and patient experience. Innovation in medicine represents a key driver for improving the quality of healthcare, promoting technological progress and stimulating economic growth. They cover a wide range of areas including medical devices, pharmaceuticals, diagnostics, treatments and healthcare management. One of the main system-forming factors that determine the effective functioning of healthcare is the development of its infrastructure and resource provision, including financial, material, technical and technological equipment of medical institutions based on innovative approaches.

MATERIAL AND METHOD(S)

1. Qualitative methods

- Interviews: Conducting in-depth interviews with experts, doctors and patients to identify needs and problems.
- Focus groups: Convening discussions with various stakeholders in the health care system to gather opinions and ideas.
- 3. Quantitative methods
- Surveys: Conducting surveys among medical workers and patients to obtain statistical data.
- Statistical Analysis: Use of statistical methods to analyze the collected data.

2. Case method

- Studying specific examples of introducing innovations in healthcare, analyzing their effectiveness and results.

Comparative analysis

Comparing different health systems and their approaches to innovation. Conclusion

Relevance. The term “innovation” appeared in the 13th century. and initially meant inventing something new, ahead of its time. Already in the 19th century. the word “innovation” is found in different fields of scientific knowledge: in natural science (changes acquired in the process of growth), in ethnography (transfer from one culture to another), in jurisprudence (the act of replacing an existing obligation with another), in linguistics (changing grammatical forms). It can be argued that already at the initial stage the common meaning of this term is manifested - this is the emergence of a new quality that did not exist before, and the methods of emergence are different: this is the transfer of what is already known to new conditions, and a gradual change, but something new always appears. Innovations in healthcare are the final result of the introduction of innovations (discoveries, results of research and development work) in order to obtain economic and social effects. An innovative approach should become a growth point for the industry; it is technological improvements that will make it possible to make a breakthrough in the development of

domestic medicine. Healthcare innovation is an expansive term. In its simplest form, it can be defined as the creation and implementation of concepts, ideas, technologies, processes, and services that benefit clinical outcomes and patient experiences. These innovations can range from simple to complex. Most of them stem from the healthcare industry's persistent guiding forces, including stringent regulations, financial limitations, and health equity. Most healthcare innovations are born of the need to overcome these industry challenges. For example, if the risk associated with a specific surgical procedure is deemed too great, innovators look for new procedures or even non-surgical options. When hospitals or networks face financial challenges, they innovate new ways to reduce spending and increase revenue. Many major healthcare organizations manage their finances by merging with and absorbing other smaller systems. In this way, they can spread their expenses over a larger network. The larger the healthcare organization grows, the more negotiating leverage it gains with insurance companies, and the better the discounts from vendors. In a massive network, these financial strategies can add up to millions of dollars each year in savings.

Innovations in medicine: In the ever-evolving world of medicine, a wave of revolutionary innovations is emerging that are changing the approach to diagnosis, treatment and the formation of a healthy lifestyle. Thanks to the introduction of advanced technologies, medicine is undergoing significant changes to improve the quality of patient care, prevent complications and create a culture of healthy lifestyles. Modern medicine is going through a period of incredible change thanks to innovative technologies. These technologies not only improve diagnostic accuracy and treatment efficiency, but also change the face of healthcare as a whole. In this article, we look at the most significant innovations in medicine that are currently revolutionizing the industry and transforming health care. As a result, many small facilities and private practices are feeling pressure to merge. Thanks to the sheer volume of savings, the larger networks can offer better services at lower costs, which makes it virtually impossible for smaller providers to compete. Healthcare innovation — especially concerning how services are delivered — could help smaller, rural health care facilities remain relevant or maintain their independence.

Materials and methods. Healthcare Innovation Artificial intelligence Medical robotics Wearable devices for Diptych health Genome analysis and editing. Implementation and augmented reality technologies. Implantable devices and prostheses. When developing recommendations for healthcare, innovation refers to certain well-known concepts, but taking into account the specifics of the industry. Innovations in the healthcare sector are intended to create effective medicines, modern medical equipment and equipment, new medical diagnostic, therapeutic, rehabilitation technologies, or organizational processes. Medical technological or process innovations are determined by the emergence of new methods, methods, methods of prevention, diagnosis and treatment based on existing drugs, the introduction of new equipment or new combinations of their use, allowing the provision of new services. Organizational and managerial innovations that implement effective restructuring of the health care system, improving the organization of work of medical personnel, organizing the reception of patients, methods of organizing the management structure. Economic innovations that ensure the implementation of modern methods of planning, financing, stimulating and analyzing the activities of healthcare institutions. Information technology innovations aimed at automating the processes of collecting, processing, and analyzing information flows in the industry. Medical-pharmaceutical, medical-technical innovations, which are a type of medical technological innovation, but which imply, as an imperative, the use of new medicines (technical systems) that are competitive in price and basic parameters of medical effectiveness.

Technical – aimed at developing and improving products or processes. Administrative – aimed at improving the organizational structure, management processes and implementation of work. at all stages (planning, ordering, enforcement).

Modern healthcare is closely related to the economy or service economy, so it seems important to focus on the feasibility of recognizing the category of service innovations in this industry. The search for solutions in the field of strategy for the development of the service sector in our society, which is the basis for improving

the quality of life of the population, is reflected in a few scientific works that do not pay due attention to positions related to medicine. Therefore, it is obviously important to combine the treatment process (introduce into the treatment process) service innovations - to provide services with qualitatively improved characteristics, introduce new ones, increase their consumer value and significance for the recovery of patients. Innovations can be carried out in isolation from each other, but more often the implementation of innovations in one area is impossible without innovative activities in another or several. In a number of economically developed countries, investments from the financial savings of the population are attracted to medicine, which allows not only to receive passive income, but also to increase the level of security of their lives. However, the social significance of the healthcare industry is given by the need in our country for state participation and regulation of innovative development. As follows from program documents and a few studies, innovative development of healthcare requires: interaction between medical science and practical healthcare, implementation and implementation of scientific innovations that are in demand in medical activities, training of professionals capable of implementing scientific developments.

Conclusions: Thus, the significance of innovations for healthcare can be represented by the following theses:

- innovations make it possible to provide higher-quality medical care, achieve a therapeutic result and, therefore, restore or improve the patient's original physical status (medical component).
- lead to a higher degree of satisfaction with the medical care of the population. Innovative activities in medicine should be determined by the needs of patients (social component).
- aimed at the payback of the treatment and diagnostic process – healthcare should be relatively economically profitable (economic component).

Product and process innovations in the healthcare system are those innovations that cover both a system for preventing and treating diseases, rehabilitating patients, creating fundamentally new drugs, new medical equipment and equipment, new information, accounting, management and other benefits that help improve the quality of medical services. The prospects for increasing the scale of healthcare financing due to the need to purchase imported expensive equipment and medicines objectively determine the need for innovative modernization of procurement principles at present. Modern innovations in medicine are transforming the way patients are diagnosed, treated and cared for. These technologies not only improve the efficiency of medical practice, but also open up new opportunities for treating previously incurable diseases. It is important that healthcare professionals stay up to date with the latest innovations and are prepared to implement them into practice to ensure the best possible health and well-being for patients.

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